

Milestone: M5.2: Mapping exercise of potential Members and relevant national bioinformatics societies in ESFRI countries

Lead Participant: ELIXIR Hub

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Due: 31 July 2025 (18)

Date Of Completion: 30/06/2025

Means of Verification

[20250731 ELIXIR-STEERS M5.2 Mapping Potential Member States \(Europe only\)](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No.

Project participants & others

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Next action steps

No further actions are required

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